

Obstacles to Adequate Funding of Agricultural Research Institute Libraries in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study focused on the obstacles to adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria. All the fifteen (15) agricultural research institute libraries were involved in the main study; three in the pilot study, and twelve in the main study. The survey research method was adopted and Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection on the Obstacles to Adequate Funding of Agricultural Research Institute Libraries in Nigeria. Questionnaires on Obstacles to Adequate Funding of Agricultural Research Institute Libraries in Nigeria. solicited responses from the principal officers of Agricultural Research Institutes and their librarians who were themselves major users of the libraries. The responses were in line with the two research objectives of the study: Obstacles to adequate funding and services rendered with received funds. The data collected were analysed using frequency distributions, percentages, mean scores, standard deviation, graphs, test of differences and relationships for the one hypothesis. PPMC was used to statistically test for the relationship between obstacles of sufficient funding and satisfactory services provision. However, obstacles to adequate funding still exist. The hypothesis was tested as significant level of 0.05. The decision of the hypothesis was rejected at $P < 0.05$ and retained at alpha level of 0.05 ($P > 0.05$). For hypothesis one, the observed P-value for the test was 0.000 compared with 0.05 fixed level of significance ($P < 0.05$). This observation provided enough evidence for rejecting the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between obstacles to sufficient funding and services provided by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria as a guide for Assessment of funding is therefore rejected. Hypothesis one was rejected. The recommendations of the study included 10% of total recurrent budgets of Agricultural Research Institutes for their libraries, better utilization of allocated funds through enhanced monitoring, statutory recognition of Agricultural Research Institutes librarians as principal officers should be enforced and so on.

Keywords: *Obstacle, Funding, Agricultural Research Institute, Libraries*

Introduction

Libraries must also facilitate maximum provision of information to their users by giving out and receiving information resources from other libraries. The quality and indeed the quantity of the services provided by the libraries of the agricultural research institutes in Nigeria will provide an adequate assessment of funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria. Some of the libraries have outdated materials, facilities, equipment and services rendered to their clients as a result of inadequate funding which led to the obstacles of funding the libraries. They ought to also undertake training and re-training and hence, capacity building of staff to meet the current challenges in librarianship. If the agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria are to perform these functions effectively therefore, they must possess adequate and appropriate information resources for effective services. All these can only be made possible with adequate funding (Tiamiyu, 1990).

There are fifteen agricultural research institutes in Nigeria and they have the following under-listed objectives for their libraries (Ezeala and Yusuff, 2011):

- i. To draw the attention of the scientists and other users to the available printed and non-printed information relevant to them in crop and animal production.
- ii. To provide relevant current and up-to date information to clients.
- iii. To develop close working relationship with individual clients so as to identify with their schedule of work, working habit and information needs.
- iv. Provide library materials in supporting faculty, external and collaborative research.
- v. Provide materials for personal development.
- vi. Provide books, journals, pamphlets, magazines, reprints, periodicals and on-line and offline services for instruction, assignments, term papers, theses, dissertations as well as supplementary readings.
- vii. Document all available information on crop and animal production in Nigeria.
- viii. Set up and manage computer database on crop and animal production research

in order to make information retrieval easier.

- ix. Serve as a clearing house for crop and animal production research information.
- x. Provide selective dissemination of information service (SDI) to the scientists and other users.
- xi. Provide outreach programs to rural communities, informing them about new practices and current developments in crop and livestock production.
- xii. Collection of research output on animal production research in Nigeria; data entries of over 3000 research abstracts from twenty Nigerian universities and bio-data on who is who in animal production research in Nigeria.

These objectives could be said to form the nucleus of the services they render to their users. Librarians and information scientists are not only concerned with the acquisition, processing, storage and dissemination of hard information to individuals and organizations for their use, but are also concerned with the manner in which the information provided is put to use in the agricultural research institute libraries (Ezeala and Yusuff, 2011). They have also become concerned with the outcomes in terms of the satisfaction derived by the recipients of the information services in carrying out their several functions (Tiamiyu, 1990).

However, this study therefore intends to investigate obstacles to adequate spending of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The obstacles that could hinder adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria is very imperative because the libraries cannot afford to remain underfunded, a situation that could totally paralyze the operations of these agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria.

The services provided by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria (ARILN) with the money given to them can no longer meet their demand. The libraries are generally mandated to serve as sources of information to support teaching and research objectives of members of

their immediate communities. This implies that these libraries need to be up-to-date and well organized for smooth and accelerated retrieval of information by scientists and other users. Uganneya, Ape and Ugbagir (2013) observed that the agricultural sector had not been doing well in the recent past and this was partly attributed to the inability of the libraries to provide resources and effective services to researchers and other stakeholders in agricultural institution. This is a problem because today, most researchers in the agricultural research institutes in Nigeria have adapted readily to the widespread availability of digital content, accessible directly from their desktops because their respective libraries can no longer meet their demand (Cullen and Calvert, 2000). Ezeala (2009) supported this observation and opined that:

This scenario has brought about a sharp fall over the past five years in the number of researchers who visit and utilize their institution's library regularly. The researchers prefer to access digital information from their desktops either from homes or their offices.

The above scenario might have arisen from inadequate funding. If the non-patronization trend is allowed to continue, the fears of these libraries slipping into redundancy and non-existence, in the next few decades, can be readily appreciated.

Objectives of the Study

This research study aims at achieving the under listed objectives:

1. To determine the obstacles to sufficient funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria.
2. To find out the services provided by the agricultural research institute libraries with the funds received, as a guide to assessment of funding.

Research Questions

The study provided answers to the following research questions:

1. What are the obstacles to adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria?

2. What are the services provided by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria with the funds received, as a guide to the assessment of funding?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was tested for this study.

1. There is no significant relationship between obstacles to sufficient funding and services provided with received funds by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria as a guide for assessment of funding.

Significance of the Study

Finally, the management and librarians as it will enable them to know the various obstacles affecting adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria with a view to correcting them.

Also, to both librarians and beneficiaries (researchers, scientists, students and other end- users) because it will enable them to know the services that can be provided by the agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria; therefore, the beneficiaries can allow their search problems to be addressed by the librarians so that they can spend more time on their research / laboratory activities.

Review of Related Literature

The obstacles to adequate funding of agricultural research institutes libraries in Nigeria cannot be over emphasized. Dennis in Charlie (2017) said the drug problem is not new in Southwest Virginia, but lack of funding for effective, long-term treatment has hurt efforts to curb the epidemic. "We are lacking in funding for treatment," he said. "We need treatment (long-term) in our area but can't get it." (Charlie, 2017). This can be related to agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria, scientists and other stakeholders of the libraries needs current and updated information services for their research work but due to underfunding of these libraries, effective and efficient services are not rendered as expected by the libraries.

Ubogu and Okiy (2011) reported that the obstacles to alternative sources of funding are librarian's attitude, inadequate philanthropic

culture of Nigerian citizens, Azubogu (2009) identified the obstacles affecting funding of research institute libraries to include: inadequate management of funds released, insensitivity on part of government, lack of public-private partnership, librarians' attitude, appointment of non-librarians as board members and inadequate attention by their management. It is therefore envisaged that, a policy that allows for the institute librarians to be part of management, may reduce management - induced obstacles to funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria.

Discrepancies and delays in the Budget process can also be obstacles to funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria. Gbolagade and Aliyu (2011) stressed that the habitual late completion of budget proposals between the National Assembly and Presidency, causes both funding approvals and disbursements to be late and often leads to conflict in the budget process. Delays have significant impact on the conduct of research, especially in terms of the period, such as seasonal farm operations and this can impact on the services of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria to scientists and other stakeholders. Planned activities spill over, into the next year as a matter of necessity. Delays in the budget process regularly cause fourth quarter disbursements to occur as late as the end of December necessitating an extension until March of the following year, which may result in inflation, thereby causing service providers to resort to over pricing and later, account for inflation and interest. Research libraries suffer from the above obstacle which eventually affect the activities of the library and automatically reflect on the services the library renders to its immediate communities (Nok, 2006, Gbolagade and Aliyu, 2011).

The allocations that are finally approved are usually based on priorities, lobby groups and personal relationships with the ministry, Budget Office and National Assembly. According to Ifidon and Okoli (2002), there is no separate budget for the libraries to spend when budgets for the institutions are approved and there is lack of uniform policy of funding their libraries, this may still be the case today. They also identified the obstacle of global economic depression and inflation, devaluation

of local currency and lack of relationship between annual subventions and estimates. Apparently budgetary delay due to National Assembly and Presidency impasse is another obstacle that is difficult to handle, as agricultural research institutes management have to wait. Another obstacle to poor funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria is that monitoring and evaluation activities should be conducted prior to the quarterly disbursement of funds, but overlapping delays make this entirely impracticable from an operational perspective. The lack of a culture which supports monitoring and evaluation further compounds this challenge. Given the dearth of qualified specialists, monitoring and evaluations are often reduced to mere field visits. As a result, the budget process is less transparent than desired and fraught by mismanagement (Ubongu and Okiy, 2011).

Obstacles to funding of research institute libraries have not really been considered by their librarians. There is no forum where agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria can come together to discuss problems that are biting hard on services provision. This is why efforts to reduce these problems to the barest minimum have not been put in place by the librarians and stakeholders. It is imperative for these obstacles to be identified so that the librarians will be able to situate agricultural research institute libraries in a vantage position to function optimally.

These obstacles to funding agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria have greatly affected their competence in providing the desired materials and services to researchers. Hence, agricultural research institute librarians in Nigeria have to be proactive in finding solution to problems affecting funding, if they are to be relevant in their institutions.

According to Grilfith (2006) services in the libraries are library processes and activities carried out with the aim of disseminating desirable information to library users. Services to users in the broadest sense include, all library functions since the ultimate aim of any library activity is the satisfaction of users' information needs. The library and information community have provided a range of services which

facilitate the inter-change of library data, promote the inter-cooperation of library systems and support the operation of national and international networking of research libraries. Also, the Australian Library Association (2006) noted these services to include: reference service, current awareness services, circulation services, selective dissemination of information services, Internet services, inter-library loan services, photocopy services and so forth.

Udekwe (2007) opined that agricultural research institute libraries also provide the following services: Access to Global Online Research in Agriculture (AGORA), Gender Agricultural Research Database (GARD), Crop Varieties Data Base (GROVAD), Media Services, Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) and Extension and Outreach Services. Majority of these, are now considered as resources. Agricultural research institute library services in this study, imply and include, from a global perspective, services provided from Internet, online and offline data base, Video Compact Disc (VCD), Digital Video Disc (DVD), flash drive, scanners, digital camera, software and print information resources (Mamman and Adejumo, 2012). Services, therefore, involve the use of the information resources to satisfy users' needs through the medium of Current Awareness Services (CAS), selective dissemination of information (SDI), Bibliographic services, inter-library loans, online services, outreach programmes, facilitating and promoting reading clubs, developing programmes for library users, managing access to electronic information resources, building collections to respond to changing community needs or demands, creating pathfinders, answering incoming reference questions via telephone, portal mail, e-mail, fax and chat, cataloguing and classification, circulation, publishing, media-services, digitization, interactive searching, Internet services and so forth. This must facilitate maximum provision of information to their users, the agricultural research institute scientists and other stakeholders, by giving out and receiving information resources from other libraries. Also inclusive are training and re-training of library staff, hence capacity building to meet the current challenges in librarianship. Computers have become part and parcel of the

library networks and the society in general and are being included as integral components of services in agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria (Fabunmi et al., 2006). The quantities and indeed the qualities of the above enumerated resources and services in any library are guided by the adequacy of the funding of such a library and hence their existence is a good assessment of funding to such a library. The libraries exist for the sake of rendering these services, the emphasis however, shouldn't just be on the services the libraries rendered, but also on how rendering these services translate into satisfaction on the part of the user of the library. This is hinged on the conception that services delivery must meet satisfaction at one point or the other.

Mwila (1993) stated that the library is considered as an integral composition of any efficient research system. It plays a vital role in the improvement of scientific and technological research and the acceleration of the innovation process. An understanding of the information needs, as well as the ways agricultural scientists and other users use their libraries is crucial to effectively meeting their information needs. Service is the major function of agricultural research institute library. Adesiji and Komolafe (2017) examined sources of funds for Technology generating activities and compared agro-technology generating practices and identified constraining factors hindering technology generating practices as poor access to knowledge and information on new innovation for universities and limited physical resources, like Information Communication Technology (ICT), Telephone, for research institutes, respectively. However, the study excluded agricultural research institutes and was limited to North central Zone. For a service to be rendered there must be a recipient who should be ready to appreciate such. However, this may not be possible if the service is not rendered properly. This also is applicable to library services. Any agricultural research institute library that has up to 70% of the under listed services serve as a guide or standard for adequate funding of the library. The services provided in agricultural research institute libraries are such that should be useful to the administration of every user (scientists) and others but the obstacles to adequate funding of

agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria did not allow the 70% achievement.

comprised of all the Principal Officers of the agricultural research institutes and the heads of their libraries in the fifteen agricultural research institutes. That is, a total population of one hundred and five (105) respondents, see Table 1.1 the breakdown of the population of the study

Methodology

The study adopts the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study

Table1: Breakdown of the Study Population (Nigerian Agricultural Research Institutes and their Libraries)

S/No	Institutes (NARIs)	Principal Officers of NARIs	Heads of Libraries of NARILs	Total Population
1.	Institute for Agricultural Research (IAR), Zaria.	6	1	7
2.	National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI), Vom.	6	1	7
3.	Nigerian Institute for Oil Palm Research (NIFOR), Benin City.	6	1	7
4.	Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T), Ibadan.	6	1	7
5.	Lake Chad Research Institute (LCRI) Maiduguri	6	1	7
6.	Rubber Research Institute of Nigeria (RRIN), Benin City.	6	1	7
7.	Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria (CRIN), Ibadan	6	1	7
8.	National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research (NIFFR), New Bussa.	6	1	7
9.	National Agricultural Extension and Research liaison services (NAERLS), Zaria.	6	1	7
10.	National Animal Production Research Institute (NAPRI), Zaria.	6	1	7
11.	National Institute for Horticultural Research (NIHORT), Ibadan.	6	1	7
12.	National Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research (NIOMR), Lagos.	6	1	7
13.	National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI), Badeggi.	6	1	7
14.	National Roots Crops Research Institute (NRCRI), Umudike.	6	1	7
15.	Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute (NSPRI), Ilorin.	6	1	7
	Total	90	15	105

NARIs= Nigerian Agricultural Research Institutes

NARILs= Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries

Source: Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria, 2010.

The sample size for the study is 84, Convenience sampling technique was used for this study. A self-developed questionnaire was used in collecting data for the study. The face and content validity of questionnaire was validated by experts. The questionnaire was administered with the help of research assistant. Data collected were analysing using inferential statistics and mean The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significant level. The decision of the hypothesis was either rejected at $p < 0.05$ or retained at alpha level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Presentation of Result

Out of the eighty-four (84) copies of the questionnaire distributed to the respondents, a total of eighty (80) copies were returned completed and found useful for this study.

Research question 1: What are the obstacles to adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria?

The opinion of the respondents on the obstacles to adequate funding of the libraries are presented in Table 2 which also shows the opinions of respondents to the listed obstacles to the adequate funding of the libraries in frequencies and percentages. Mean scores were computed for the respective items based on the five-point scale with 3.0 for midpoint decision. The percentages are graphically illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 2: Obstacles to Adequate Funding of the Agricultural Research Institute Libraries in Nigeria

	Strongly Agreed		Agreed		Undecided		Disagreed		Strongly Disagreed		Mean
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
Obstacles to adequacy of funding the Institute libraries											
Misapplication of funds by the management is an obstacle to adequate funding of my library.	9	11.3	16	20	11	13.8	26	32.5	18	22.5	2.7
Inadequate attention by the management to the issue of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries is an obstacle to funding.	12	15	25	31.3	8	10	18	22.5	17	21.3	3
Lack of accountability and transparency by the librarians is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	4	5	12	15	9	11.3	31	38.8	24	30	2.3
Inadequate public-private partnership is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	11	13.8	39	48.8	9	11.3	11	13.8	10	12.5	3.4
Appointment of non-librarians as board members is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	12	15	13	16.3	19	23.8	20	25	16	20	2.8
Librarian is not among principal officers of institutes, is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	9	11.3	12	15	11	13.8	25	31.3	23	28.8	2.5
Librarian is not proactive and or does not defend library developmental proposals is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute libraries.	6	7.5	14	17.5	10	12.5	30	37.5	20	25	2.5
Discrepancies and delay in the budget process is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	17	21.3	41	51.3	5	6.3	8	10	9	11.3	3.6
Lack of cordial relationship between librarians and the Executive Director is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	9	11.3	10	12.5	7	8.8	30	37.5	24	30	2.4
Misappropriation of budgeted funds is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	11	13.8	16	20	11	13.8	26	32.5	16	20	2.8
Is there separate budget for library from the institutional budget as an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries	3	3.8	19	23.8	21	26.3	19	23.8	18	22.5	2.6
Economic depression and inflation is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	19	23.8	37	46.3	8	10	10	12.5	6	7.5	3.7

Devaluation of local currency is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	16	20	25	31.3	12	15	17	21.3	10	12.5	3.3
Denial of the actual budget allocated by government to libraries by Executive Directors is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	18	22.5	21	26.3	6	7.5	18	22.5	17	21.3	3.1
Lack of monitoring and evaluation culture to support the libraries is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	11	13.8	31	38.8	9	11.3	20	25	9	11.3	3.2
Lack of qualified specialist on monitoring and evaluation team is often reduced to mere field visits is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	12	15	23	28.8	16	20	15	18.8	14	17.5	3.1
The result of No 16 results to the budget being less transparent than desired and challenged by management is an obstacle to adequate funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	5	6.3	26	32.5	19	23.8	17	21.3	13	16.3	2.9
Low allocation of funds by Federal Government to libraries is an obstacle to funding of Nigerian Agricultural Research Institute Libraries.	40	50	34	42.5	3	3.8	2	2.5	1	1.3	4.4

Foremost in the obstacles to adequate funding of the libraries was the low allocation of funds by Federal Government to the agricultural research institute libraries. This was the unanimous factor of the inadequacy in the funding of the libraries and in Table 4.2 where the mean score is 4.4, which was the opinion of almost every respondent involved in the study. This is clearly shown in the graph and the high rate of agreement and percentage scores in the table. Next to this obstacle was the economic depression and inflation suffered in the country resulting in the devaluation of the Nigerian Naira, which made exchange rate and purchase of library materials very difficult to procure outside the country. In the table, the mean score for the item is 3.7. The finding is in agreement with the study of Uganneya (2012) that challenges in acquisition of library materials, qualified librarians, outdated tools for service delivery and poor infrastructural development led to a high level of scantiness over the years and subsequent lack of patronage by researchers (scientists) for whom retrieval of research information was required, to meet research institutes' mandates

Other major obstacles included discrepancies and delay in the budget processes, inadequate public-private partnership, devaluation of local currency, lack of monitoring and evaluation culture to support the libraries, denial of the actual budget allocated by government to libraries by Executive Directors, lack of qualified specialists on monitoring and evaluation teams which are often reduced to mere field visits by such personnel and therefore made no meaning to the actual evaluation of the funding and finally, inadequate attention by the management to the issue of agriculture research institute libraries. These were scored in Table 4.2 at the midpoint of 3.0 and clearly indicated in Figure. 4.1 above. This finding agrees with the report of Gbolagade and Aliyu (2011) who stressed that the habitual late completion of budget proposals between the National Assembly and Presidency caused both funding approvals and disbursements to be late and often led to conflict in the budget process.

Other obstacles like misapplication of funds by the management, lack of accountability and transparency by the librarians, appointment of non-librarians as

board members, non-inclusion of librarians among principal officers of institutes, the inability of Librarian to be proactive and defend library developmental proposals, lack of cordial relationship between librarians and the Executive Directors, misappropriation of budgeted funds and the inability to have a separate budget for the library along with non-transparency in budgeting were not considered as major obstacles to the sufficiency of funding the institute libraries.

The implication is that, the obstacle to adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria had made planning difficult for the libraries.

Research Question 2: What are the services provided by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria with the funds received, as a guide to the assessment of funding?

Among the services analyzed were abstracting and indexing, Internet services for users, photocopying services, literature search services, current awareness services and selective dissemination of information services. Also, the respondents' opinions on their agreement with the selected services are presented in Table 3 with graphical illustration of the percentage scores in Figure2. The table shows the mean score for the respective items computed on a five-point scale. Decision on items were based on the midpoint score of 3.0 mean score lower than 3.0 would therefore mean that the respondents disagreed with the notion expressed for the item.

Table 3: Services Provided with Received Funds by Agricultural Research Institute Libraries in Nigeria, as a guide to Assessment of Funding.

Services provided by the libraries to their users	Strongly Agreed		Agreed		Undecided		Disagreed		Strongly Disagreed		Mean
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
My library provides Internet services for its users 24 hours daily.	11	13.8	27	33.8	6	7.5	23	28.8	13	16.3	3.0
My library provides customer services to its clients.	26	32.5	45	56.3	6	7.5	1	1.3	2	2.5	4.2
My library provides photocopying services to its users.	22	27.5	38	47.5	4	5.0	12	15.0	4	5.0	3.8
My library assists users on literature search when they need it.	29	36.3	48	60	2	2.5	1	1.3			4.3
My library provides reference services to its users.	34	42.5	42	52.5	1	1.3	1	1.3	2	2.5	4.3
My library provides current awareness services to its users.	15	18.8	45	56.3	11	13.8	7	8.8	2	2.5	3.8
My library provides selective dissemination of information service to its users.	14	17.5	45	56.3	10	12.5	10	12.5	1	1.3	3.8
My library provides circulation services to its users.	19	23.8	37	46.3	17	21.3	5	6.3	2	2.5	3.8
My library provides extension and outreach services to its users.	11	13.8	34	42.5	16	20	13	16.3	6	7.5	3.4
My library provides media service to its users.	9	11.3	24	30	22	27.5	17	21.3	8	10	3.1
My library provides mobile library services to its users.	3	3.8	8	10	11	13.8	35	43.8	23	28.8	2.2
My library provides abstracting and indexing services to its users.	16	20	44	55	9	11.3	8	10	3	3.8	3.8

Key: Mean $\bar{X} = \sum fx / \sum f$

\bar{X} = Mean

Σ = Sum

f = Frequency (Number of Respondents)

x = Strongly Agreed (SA) =5, Agreed (A) = 4, Undecided (U) =3, Disagreed (D) =2, Strongly Disagreed (SD) =1

From the mean scores in Table 3 and the graphical illustration in Figure 2 above, the libraries provided to their users all the services listed on the table with the use of Mobile services being the only exception to what they offered. This fact was revealed by the frequencies and percentage of strongly agree, and the mean score of 2.2 on the table and the chart clearly supported this observation. It could therefore be said that the libraries provided Internet services, photocopying services, literature search, reference services, current awareness services, selective dissemination of information service, circulation services, extension and outreach services, media service and abstracting and indexing services to their users. This finding is consistent with the report of Udekwe (2007) who opined that agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria provided the following services: Media Services, Extension and Outreach Services. The Australian Library Association (2006) also listed other services such as reference services, current awareness services, circulation services, selective dissemination of information services, Internet services, Inter-Library Loan services and photocopying services. Of the services provided by the agricultural research institutes' libraries with funds received, only mobile service was not provided in this study. The implication is that, this may only slightly affect service provision at the outstations of these institutes, as this mobile service is essential for extension workers in the institutes.

Test of Hypothesis

The hypothesis was aimed at determining differences in the obstacles of sufficient funding of the libraries as well as to establish relationship between funding obstacles and the investigated variables relating to the services delivery of the libraries. The data collected with respect to the hypothesis raised in the studies were analyzed and discussed. The hypothesis was tested as follows:

Hypothesis I: There is no significant relationship between Obstacles to sufficient funding and services provided with received funds by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria as a guide for assessment of funding

This hypothesis was tested with the mean score on obstacles to sufficient fund allocated to the libraries in Table 2 and services provided with received funds by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria as a guide for assessment of funding in Table 3. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) procedure was adopted for the test because of the quantitative measurement of the variables involved and the result is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation between Obstacles to sufficient Funding and Services Provided with Received Funds by Agricultural Research Institute Libraries in Nigeria as a guide for Assessment of Funding.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	r-calc.	DF	P	Decision
Utilization	80	3.27	0.870	0.097	0.392	78	0.000	
Satisfactory Services	80	3.37	0.776	0.087				Rejected

(r-critical =0.217, P< 0.05)

The result in Table 4.4 reveals that obstacles to sufficient funding allocated to the libraries was significantly correlated with services provided with received funds by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria as a guide for assessment of funding. The observed correlation coefficient (0.392) for the test was higher than the critical value of (0.217) at the 78 degrees of freedom. The observed P-value for the test was 0.000 compared with 0.05 fixed level of significance ($P < 0.05$). These observations provided enough ground for rejecting the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between obstacles to sufficient funds and services provided with received funds by agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria as a guide for assessment of funding is therefore rejected. The finding here agrees with Adeniyi (2007), who reported that the availability of relevant information materials, modern reference and documentation services and information and communication facilities could positively influence research and extension works of the institutes.

Summary of the Major Findings

The study revealed that:

- i. The obstacles to adequate funding of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria, were low budgetary allocation; economic depression and inflation; discrepancies and delay in the budget process; inadequate public - private partnership; devaluation of local currency; lack of monitoring and evaluation culture to support the libraries; denial of actual budget allocated by government to libraries by Executive Directors; lack of qualified

specialists on monitoring and evaluation team often reduced to mere field visits; inadequate attention by the management to issue of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria.

- ii. Services provided by the agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria with funds received were Internet, Photocopy, Literature search, Reference, Customer and Current Awareness services, Selective Dissemination of Information, Extension and outreach, Media, Abstracting and Indexing Services, except mobile services.

Conclusion

Low budgetary allocation by government constituted a major challenge to the funding of these libraries as high level of inconsistency in budgetary allocation militate against smooth planning and execution of objectives in the libraries, if the challenges of inadequate funding, appropriate budgetary allocation and establishment of the right channel for fund allocation are adequately addressed, the service delivery of these libraries would probably improve beyond the level it is presently.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby made based on the findings and conclusions reached for in the study.

1. Allocation of 10% of total recurrent budgets of ARIs should be made available by the Federal Government for their libraries in order to improve services provision by agricultural research institute

libraries in Nigeria, the librarian of each agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria should be a Principal Officer of the respective institute to enable the librarian to have a meaningful understanding of funds allocations and there should be effective monitoring of funds to the libraries by the institutes and government teams.

2. Library staff should be trained and encouraged to discover more current services that are better for the users and beneficiaries (researchers or scientists and students) of agricultural research institute libraries in Nigeria.

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